

A STUDY ON PASSENGER SATISFACTION IN RAILWAY RESERVATION SYSTEM

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Cite This Article: S. Samundeeswari & M. Muthamilselvi, "A Study on Passenger Satisfaction in Railway Reservation System", International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, International Peer Reviewed - Refereed Research Journal, Volume 10, Issue 1, January - June, Page Number 52-54, 2024.

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Abstract:

The railway reservation system facilitates the passengers to enquiry about the trains available on the basis of source and destination, booking and cancellation of tickets, enquiry about the status of the booked ticket, etc. The aim of case study is to design and develop a data base maintaining records of different trains, train status and passengers. This project contains introduction to the railways reservation system. It is the computerized system of reserving the seats of train seats in advance. It is mainly used for a long route. Online reservation has made the process for the reservation of seats very much easier than ever before.

Key Words: Features of the System, General Booking, Premium Tatkal Booking, Problems and Solution.

Introduction:

Railway reservation system is developed for to automate the railways reservation system. It includes modules required to successfully operate railways reservation process smoothly. It has train master to add modified train information, train schedule to enter train journey details include all the station name, arrival time and departure time. It includes automatic fair calculation as per the distance between two stations. Reservation module consists of automatic seat number and coaches' allocation system. Daily schedule for updating of non conform seat and coach numbers. All master like train master, Train schedule, reservation fees, cancellation fees, charges can be modified individually from front end and changes reflect in all modules immediately. Therefore proposed "Railway reservation system" has been designed to automate the process of railway for ticket reservation and back office activities. System can make the daily activities efficient and provide the fast response.

The "Railway reservation system" has been developed to override the problems prevailing in the practicing manual system. This software is supported to eliminate and in some cases reduce the hardships faced by this existing system. Moreover this system is designed for a particular need of a company to carry out operations in a smooth and effective manner. The application is reduced has much as possible to avoid errors while entering the data. It also provides error messages while entering invalid data. No formal knowledge is needed for the user to use this system. Thus by this all it proves it is user friendly. Railway reservation system, has described, can lead to error free, and secure, reliable and fast managing system. It can assist the user to concentrate on the other activities rather to concentrate on the record keeping. Thus it will help organization in better utilization of resources. Every organization, whether big or small, has challenges to overcome and managing the information of ticket, train, customer, seat, payment. Every Railway reservation system has different train needs; therefore we designed exclusive employee management systems that are adapted to your managerial requirements.

Objectives:

- To identify the problem faced by the passengers while on booking the tickets.
- To analysis the level of Train passenger satisfaction.

Review of Literature:

Alan Williams (2006) survey said that, our passenger want is seemed simple enough friendly staff, safer station, comfortable, clean train than ran on time, reservation facilities and to be kept informed. However, the survey soon realized that to do the consistently well, we had to changes from an operation driven railway to one the passenger at the heart of the business. The survey also suggested that the improvement can be made in the pipeline is the replacement of all tick machines. To make a replacement of all machines across the network as well as providing additional equipment at the busiest station and they will accept credit and chip-and-pin enabled. At the same time, upgrading our booking offices so that they too, can use the latest technology to provide time table information and make seat reservation instantly.

Amithabh Pandey (2002) discussed about the e-commerce / e-governance initiative began in India and its importance. His study, mainly focus on the purpose of railway ticket booking through internet as one of the

largest and fastest growing G2C ventures in India. And the network Passenger Reservation System, online booking of railway tickets would not have been possible. The task of computerizing back office operation is after difficult and low profile, but it must be done before useful citizen centric application can be developed. His study gives importance to the awareness of and willingness to use the internet is spreading rapidly in India.

W. H, Bocheng Chen, Henry C.W. Lau and Bing Liang (2006) Propose a functioned framework based on passenger value to realize the win-win strategy for the companies and their customer. Moreover a workflow management system also forms an integral part of this total solution to facilitate the implementation of a supply chain or extended enterprise. They reveal that integration of business partners, suppliers, and customers is essential in this global competitive market environment.

Christopher Gore (2002) discussed in his paper that the British Railway reviewed the management of environment issue in 1989. Analysis had revealed a diverse range of concerns. Responsibility was devolved to business units; sensation managers and the workforce has been a key objective. Operator licenses issued by the Regulator in the new fragmented structure of the industry will require progress to be maintained.

Judy C. R Tseng and Gwo-Jen Hwang (2007) proposes a customer service system, which can automatically handle customer requests by analyzing the contents of the requests and finding the most feasible answers from the frequently asked question (FAQ) database. Experimental results on practical application showed that over 87.3 % of users were satisfied with the replies given by the system; therefore, it is concluded that the system can significantly reduce the service cost and provide more efficient and effective customer service.

The Features of Reservation System:

- If a passenger wants to reserve ticket, firstly, he/she has to log in to the Railway system with valid credentials. Then, the passenger has to provide his/her details with the date of the journey, names of the passengers and their details, origin station details, destination station details, and the class type of the required ticket.
- The Railway Reservation System will provide the available Train-list, and Seat-availability, via-details.
- To book a ticket passenger can pay through online/offline mode. After successful payment of the ticket fare the System will generate the ticket and PNR no. will be given to the passenger. The System also keeps the payment details and sends them to the system Admin.
- The Passenger can check PNR status by entering the PNR no. into the Reservation system.
- The Reservation system should store all train details, fare details PNR no, date of trains, etc. This maintenance should be controlled by the Admin.
- The System also has refund rules which have a date of reservation, ticket fare, and refundable percentage. The passenger can simply cancel the ticket by entering the PNR no and a cancel ticket request. After cancellation, the Admin will pass the refundable amount to the System and the System will give the refundable amount to the passenger.

General Booking of Indian Railway Reservation System:

It is the most common type of seat booking under the reservation system provided by IRCTC. General reservations can be made both either online and offline. However, keeping the current scenario in mind, it is prudent to use the online method. A traveller booking through this quota must first select their favourite app's source and destination journey stations.

Then after selecting their train and coaches, they have to provide their basic passenger details like Name, Age, Mobile Number, E-mail ID, and other few details. After that, they can opt for their preferences, if any. Travellers can enter their GST details if any, and they can opt for travelling Insurance, which is provided as a checklist while booking.

After making the choices and declaring the same, one has to make a payment (including some agent and gateway charges in case booking is done through online mode). After payment confirmation, passengers get confirmed seats, sometimes RAC (Reservation after Cancellation), passenger tickets are generated with a unique PNR (Passenger Name Record) and are sent on their respective mobile number and email ID.

Tatkal Booking of Indian Railway Reservation System:

This quota is for emergency booking. Passengers want to book our seats on a short notice period; this quota is undoubtedly handy for that. Like its name, this reservation category is available only 24 hours before the departure of the train and it is on a first-come, first-serve basis. Also, the fare under tatkal is always higher than the regular ticket booking. The booking time window opens at 10 AM for AC coaches while 11 IS for Non- AC coaches.

Premium Tatkal Booking in Indian Railway Reservation System:

This booking is, in actuality, a premium version of the tatkal booking. Launched in 2014 as a substitute for tatkal, booking charges through this are pretty higher than that in tatkal. The booking timing is the same as that of the tatkal booking. The dynamic prices under this booking system allow confirmed seats for the passenger and are usually double that of tatkal.

The significant difference between premium tatkal and tatkal is that Premium tatkal is only available if you book a ticket via the IRCTC website, while anyone likes general booking. One can book tatkal tickets online or traditionally through Railway ticket counters, while Premium tatkal cannot. Another significant difference is while Premium tatkal gives travellers time for booking while tatkal booking exhaust itself as soon as it is available. In Premium tatkal, there is no concession policy such as a child fare is as similar as the total price for an adult. However, one can't book RAC and waiting list tickets under this Indian Railway Reservation System.

Problems and Solution:

- Technical Issues: Slow internet connection, website errors, or payment gateway issues can hinder the booking process.
- Limited Availability: Popular routes or travel dates may have limited seat availability, leading to difficulty in securing a ticket.
- Payment Problems: Credit card declines, payment gateway errors, or issues with international transactions can be obstacles.
- Complex Itineraries: Booking multiple train segments or adding special requests like seat preferences can complicate the booking process.
- User Experience: Navigating through complex booking forms or understanding the various fare options can be challenging for some problems.

Conclusion:

The Researchers of this study is the identification of problems and satisfaction to determine train passenger with the quality of services provided by the ticket booking/reservation. The service offering by Indian railway is vital for its growth. The satisfaction of the need of the passengers is important to compete with other mode of transport. On the basis of this study some suggestions has been made. If the suggestive measurements have been considered by the Indian Railways, it is hope that the Indian Railways will shine and bring grandeur to our country in the near future.

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